
38. The Magellanic Clouds

THE MAGELLANIC CLOUDS are two ‘nearby’ irregular dwarf galaxies, visible to the unaided eye in the dark skies of the southern hemisphere. They became known in Europe following Portuguese voyages in the 16th century, and in particular through Ferdinand Magellan’s circumnavigation of the world of 1519–1522.

Compared to our own Galaxy’s diameter of about 100 000 ly (light-years; divide by 3.26 if you prefer your distances in pc), the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) has a diameter of 14 000 ly, and lies 160 000 ly away. The Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC) has a diameter of 7 000 ly, and lies about 200 000 ly away. The two are separated by 20° on the sky, 75 000 ly apart in distance. Only the smaller Sagittarius Dwarf Elliptical Galaxy (discovered in 1994), and the Canis Major Dwarf Galaxy (discovered in 2003) are our more proximate neighbours.

Both probably have large dark matter halos. The LMC is now believed to be the fourth most massive of over 50 galaxies comprising the ‘Local Group’. Observations and theory suggest that the Magellanic Clouds have both been distorted by tidal interaction with the Milky Way. Their gravity has, in turn, affected the Milky Way, distorting the outer parts of our Galaxy’s disk.

WHETHER THE LMC and SMC are bound as orbital companions to our Milky Way remains uncertain. If they are, their orbital period is at least 4 billion years. The other possibility is that they are on a ‘first approach’, and we are witnessing the start of a galactic merger that may overlap with the Milky Way’s expected merger with the Andromeda galaxy sometime in the future.

In radio images sensitive to neutral hydrogen, the LMC reveals a clear spiral structure. Streams of neutral gas connect them both to the Milky Way (the Magellanic Stream) and to each other (the Magellanic Bridge). They are both gas-rich, with a higher fraction of their mass in hydrogen and helium compared to the Milky Way, and both are also more metal-poor than the Milky Way.

They both host nebulae and young stellar populations, with stars ranging from the very young to the very old, telling of a long stellar formation history.

DETERMINING THE DISTANCE to the Large Magellanic Cloud in particular has been a long-standing challenge in astronomy, representing an important early step in establishing the overall distance scale in the Universe, and hence also the associated Hubble constant.

However, its stars are far too distant for any direct geometrical (parallax) determination, even for Hipparcos. Seen from a distance of 160 000 ly (about 50 000 pc), a star’s parallax is a minuscule 20 micro-arcsec, a factor 50 smaller than the angles accessible to Hipparcos!

Angular accuracy aside, Hipparcos could observe only a few LMC and SMC stars because of its magnitude limit of around 11–12 mag, as well as very strict crowding constraints related to the functioning of its on-board detection system. A careful pre-selection of stars, satisfying these various constraints, resulted in just 36 LMC and 11 SMC objects in the observing programme of Hipparcos, all with final accuracies of around 1.5–2 milli-arcsec.

PRE-GAIA, distance estimates to the LMC were based on a consensus of various methods, each providing individual steps in a somewhat shaky distance ‘ladder’. These drew together estimates from Population I stars (Cepheids, red clump giants, Mira variables, and eclipsing binaries), Population II stars (subdwarf fitting to globular clusters, horizontal branch stars, and RR Lyrae stars), as well as white dwarf sequencing, and estimates based on the bright supernova, SN 1987A.

As I wrote in ‘Astronomical Applications of Astronomy’ in 2009: *‘Further in the future, one-step trigonometric parallax estimates to individual objects in the LMC will become accessible to Gaia. At that point, the tortuous complexity underlying the various distance estimates used to date will be relegated to historical curiosity, and still deeper insights into the physical nature of the ‘standard candles’ used to date will commence.*

I WANTED TO RECALL the Hipparcos results on the Magellanic Clouds because the step-change in what was state-of-the-art in space science just 20 years ago, and the Gaia results of today, are indeed spectacular.

Gaia view of the LMC and SMC, colour denoting populations

Gaia Early Data Release 3 (EDR3) was made available on 3 December 2020. It is based on the 34-month of satellite data obtained between July 2014 and May 2017. With respect to the earlier DR2 it includes proper motions improved by a factor 2, along with much improved photometry.

The Magellanic Clouds are close to the distance limits at which even the Gaia data accuracy starts to break down. Nonetheless, the enormous improvement in accuracy and numbers of stars represents a paradigm shift in understanding their structure and kinematics. A first assessment has been published by Luri et al. (2021), from which the following is a brief summary.

THEIR SELECTION of stars as likely members of the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds used carefully chosen criteria based on each star's position, parallax, and proper motion. This was necessary both to remove foreground contamination from our Milky Way star populations, and also to allow a proper separation of the stars belonging to each. Further division according to star colour allowed the classification of stars into groups of similar approximate age and evolutionary phase.

Starting from a coarse selection of more than 27 million Gaia objects within a 20° radius for the LMC, and more than 4 million objects within a 11° radius for the SMC, further refinement according to proper motion and parallax led to a total of 11 156 431 objects belonging to the LMC, and 1 728 303 belonging to the SMC.

The fact that Gaia measures high-accuracy photometry in a number of spectral bands (and at the same time as the astrometry) is crucial: it allows the construction of the diagnostic 'colour-magnitude diagram'. Like the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram, this can be used to categorise each star according to its evolutionary phase.

Accordingly, the members of the LMC and SMC can be further subdivided by age, notably as very young main sequence (ages < 50 Myr), young (50–400 Myr), and intermediate-age (up to 1–2 Gyr) main-sequence populations. In addition, we can identify stars of the red giant branch, the asymptotic giant branch (including long-period variables), RR Lyrae stars, classical Cepheids, and red clump stars.

ALL OF THIS allows the ordered and random motions for multiple stellar evolutionary phases to be separated for a galaxy disk outside the Milky Way for the first time, and allows the spatial structure and motions in the central region, the bar, and the disk to be examined.

THE LARGE Magellanic Cloud is taken as the prototype of the class of barred Magellanic spiral galaxies, characterised by an off-centre bar and one prominent spiral arm. The dynamical interactions between the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds are probably responsible for this and its other spiral features.

Given the huge numbers of stars in each of the LMC and SMC, future modelling is expected to reveal much more about their three-dimensional structure, their orientation with respect to the line-of-sight, and their precise distances. Meanwhile, the stellar density maps from Gaia reveal more concentrated and clumpier distributions for younger stars in the bar and inner spiral structure than the older disk stars.

Smoothed maps of the proper motion field, revealing the bulk stellar motions, shows a clear ordered rotation of the LMC, while the SMC is more chaotic. And we see that younger stars rotate faster than the older ones.

One of the most prominent features in the outskirts of these and other interacting galaxies is the existence

of a bridge between them. This is due to tidal forces that strip gas and stars from the least to the most massive galaxy. The relative position of the Milky Way with respect to the LMC and SMC places us in the privileged position of witnessing the close encounter between them, and of studying the Magellanic Bridge.

USING TWO different evolutionary phases (the young stars, and the red clump samples), Luri et al. (2021) could trace the density and velocity flow of the stars from the SMC towards the LMC following the Magellanic Bridge. The Gaia data shows that it appears to wrap around the LMC, connecting with the young southern arm-like structure. Additionally, the outskirts of both Magellanic Clouds reveal other well-known features, such as the north and south tidal arms of the LMC and the northern enhancement in density of the SMC.

The next major data release scheduled for 2022, and further releases beyond that, will shed much further light on these majestic neighbours that encode so many details of star formation and galaxy evolution.

Rotation of the LMC visualised by Gaia